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RADNEXT Transnational Access Summary Report

Project title	<i>Training CNNs to Deal with Neutrons-Induced Errors</i>
Project TA identifier	<i>TA05-94</i>
General application	<i>High-reliability ground level</i>
Type of test	<i>SEE</i>
Group leader, Institute	<i>Paolo Rech, University of Trento</i>
Dates of the experiment	<i>11-13 December 2022</i>
Facility	<i>ChipIR</i>
Amount of access granted	<i>48 hours</i>

Objectives of the experiments

The goal of this experiment is to measure the benefits, in terms of reliability, of re-trained neural networks. Deep Neural Networks (DNNs) enable a wide series of technological advancements, ranging from clinical imaging, to predictive industrial maintenance and autonomous driving. However, recent findings indicate that transient hardware faults may corrupt the models prediction dramatically. For instance, the radiation-induced misprediction probability can be as high as to prevent a safe deployment of DNN models at scale, urging the need for efficient and effective hardening solutions. In this experiment, we tackled the reliability issue both at training and model design time. We know from previous experiments that DNNs are highly susceptible to transient faults, which can induce a detection accuracy drop up to 37%. We have designed three zero-overhead reliability solutions, based on DNN re-design and re-train, that, based on our evaluation, should improve DNNs reliability to faults up to one order of magnitude. In this experiment we had experimentally validated the effectiveness of our hardening solutions.

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Experiment test report

We exposed modern GPUs (NVIDIA Volta) and modern EdgeAI devices (Google TPU) to high energy neutrons, mounted as showed in Fig. 1. We executed the original (unhardened) DNNs and then the reliable models we have designed.

Fig. 1: beam setup at ChipIR

We used the same setup and the same hardware we designed for testing DNNs with high energy neutrons in the past, including software and hardware watchdogs to detect crashes and hangs. While the GPU, or the EdgeAI, device is irradiated we ran neural networks and check for mismatches in the output. We logged all the information provided by the device, so to be sure to have a clear view of the effect and the propagation of faults. In post-processing we identify the faults that are more likely to modify the autonomous vehicle behavior and the sources of those faults. We validated the improved reliability by comparing the error rate (output of the DNN last layer) and the failure rate (mispredictions) of the original and hardened models executed on the same device. We tested three DNN models, designed with four incremental hardening solutions.

Fig 2: weights distribution of the hardened vs baseline DNN

As shown in Fig 2, the weights distribution of the hardened DNN is more spread than the baseline, suggesting that our training has an impact in the inference of the DNN.

Each model and configuration has been tested in three different GPUs. That is, we gathered more than 100 SDCs on each of the 12 configurations tested. In particular, we have seen that the hardened DNN, thanks to a fault-aware training, experienced a much lower number of critical errors (misdetections) than the plain DNN. Fig. 3 shows an overview of our results, reporting the percentage of critical SDCs, the test accuracy (i.e., the neural network accuracy in the absence of faults) and the inference time (the execution time of the DNN, which is kept constant in the hardened version).

Fig 3: overview of the results

Interestingly, the number of Silent Data Corruptions (i.e., errors at the output) is almost constant among the tested configurations. However, what changes is the way these errors are digested by the code. Since we have trained the DNNs to detect the correct objects even in the presence of errors, in the hardened DNNs the number of misdetections is halved. This interesting result is confirmed in three different GPUs and in three different DNN models.

Outcome of the experiments

Please indicate what the experiment is likely to lead to by putting an 'X' next to one or more of the possible outcomes below.

Journal publication	X
Data for Thesis	X
Follow-up experiment at same facility	X
Follow-up experiment at another facility	X
Other	

As a RADNEXT user, we encourage you to submit the scientific results of your experiments to journals as well as to the NSREC and RADECS data workshops. Please remember to include the RADNEXT acknowledgment into your publications!

RADNEXT acknowledgment:

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